

ENROLMENT OF TRIBAL GIRLS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS OF ODISHA

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Abstract :

Education is essential for all and is fundamental to their all round development, material and spiritual. From the human history Education has continued to evolve insight. There are 62 tribes in Orissa out of which juang tribe is one of them. The enrolment ratio of Tribal girls are very low in comparisons to general category in Dhenkanal district. Many plans and Policies had been implemented to up lift the ST girls in education sector but still government is an elusive goal. This paper high lights about the causes of low enrolment in tribal girls of kankadahard block of dhenkanal district. The case study method was adopted for the study. The data were collected with ethnographic approach and on the basis of the findings researcher suggest some measures for increasing the enrolment status of Tribal Girls

Key words: Tribal girls. Enrolment, secondary school

Overview of the study :

Education is essential for all and is fundamental to their all round development, material and spiritual.. Every country develops its system of education to express and promote its unique socio-cultural identity and also to meet the growing challenges with the changing times. Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan (RMSA): This scheme is being implemented in India keeping the objective to enhance access to secondary education and improve its quality. The schemes also focuses to enhance the enrolment ratio at secondary stage by providing a secondary school within a reasonable distance of habitation, it also has one objective to ensure GER of 100% by 2017 and universal retention by 2020. The other objectives include improving quality of education imparted at secondary level through making all secondary schools conform to prescribed norms, removing gender, socio-economic and disability barriers, etc. construction and running of Girls' Hostel for students of secondary and higher secondary schools is another objective of this scheme is to improve access to and retain the girl child in secondary and higher secondary classes (IX-XII) so that the girl students are not denied the opportunity to continue their study due to distance to school, parents' financial affordability and other connected societal factors.

Table-1

S2.3: Percentage Enrolment of 'ST' students to all categories			
Year	Primary	Upper Primary	Secondary
1995-1996	8.8	6.1	4.9
1996-1997	9.2	6.3	4.9
1998-1999	9.6	6.7	5.1
1999-2000	9.4	6.9	5.0
2000-2001	9.7	7.2	5.4
2002-2003	9.7	6.9	5.4
2003-2004	9.8	7.5	5.6
2004-2005	10.5	8.1	5.6
2005-2006	10.6	8.5	5.7
2006-2007	10.8	8.5	6.1
2007-2008	10.8	8.2	6.3
2009-2010	11.2	8.6	6.3
2010-2011	11.0	8.7	6.4

Source: Selected Educational Statistics, M/HRD, 2010-11

As can be seen from the table above, some improvement in the percentage enrolment of ST students to all categories has been made in 2010-11 since 95-96, at the Primary, Upper Primary and Secondary level.

Table-2 Enrolment by Stages of School Education of ST Students – Pre-Primary, Primary, Upper-Primary-2010-11

	Pre primary			Primary (I-V)			Upper Primary (VI-VIII)		
	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total
India	565371	521540	1086911	7674617	7177742	14852359	2837031	2584718	5421749
Odisha	0	0	0	684634	654098	1338732	210031	184846	394877

Source - Statistics in school education 2010-2011

Table-3

Dropout Rates (Classes I to X) below).

S2.5: Drop Out Rates (DoR) (in percent)							
Class	Boys		Girls		Total		
	ST	All	ST	All	ST	All	Gap
Classes I - V	37.2	28.7	33.9	25.1	35.6	27	8.6
Classes I - VIII	54.7	40.3	55.4	41	55	40.6	14.4
Classes I - X	70.6	50.4	71.3	47.9	70.9	49.3	21.6

Source: Statistics Of School Education 2010-2011

Dropout rate is a critical indicator reflecting lack of educational development and inability of a given social group to complete a specific level of education. The above Table shows reveal that out of every 100 ST students who entered class-I, while almost 67 completed class V, only 41.9 completed class VIII and 13.9 studied upto class XII. The comparative data for all categories is that of 100 students entering class I, 79 completed class V, about 64 completed class VIII and 30.3 studied upto class XII. For ST students the inflection points at completion of class VIII have to be urgently addressed. According to the Statistics of School

Education 2010-11, MoHRD, the comparison of number of Scheduled Tribe girls per 100 ST boys reveal that there are 94 girls in Classes I-V, 91 girls in Classes VI-VIII, 81 girls in Classes IX-X and 72 girls per 100 boys in Classes IX-XII (Table 2.15) The comparison of the Number of Girls per hundred boys for the STs is shown in the graph below:

Table-4

State	Name of the tribe	Number Of Households	Total Population			Literacy %		
			Male	Female	Total	Total	Male	Female
Odisha	All Schedule Tribes	2232334	47,27,732	48,63,024	95,90,756	41.2	49.7	48.9
Odisha	Juang	10996	23093	24002	47095	42.8	54.9	31.4

Total population of ST and juang tribes of odisha and percentage of literacy

The above table speaks about the total no juang tribes lives in odisha . according to the tribal statistics 2013 the total no of household juang tribes are 10996 mostly found in keonjhar , dhenkanal and angul district of Odisha . the total population of juang tribes are 47095 with 23093 male 24002 are female . the total literacy of juang tribes is 42.8% .. The population of all ST in odisha is 9590756 and percentage of literacy is 41.2% with male female breakup is 49.7% and 48.9% respectively

NATIONAL SCHEME OF INCENTIVE TO GIRLS FOR SECONDARY EDUCATION (NSIGSE)

National Scheme of Incentive to Girls for Secondary Education was launched in May 2008 keeping the objective to establish an enabling environment to reduce the drop-outs and to promote the enrolment of girl children belonging mainly to SC/ST communities in secondary schools..

Review of related Studies :

The researcher collect the review on the basis of i) what are the constraints on girl's enrolment in Secondary Education.; ii) Is secondary education offered to girls in rural communities Rout(1989) conducted a study on problems related to stagnation and absenteeism among students and teachers. He finds the parental indifference towards education poverty and engagement of children in economic activities, early mirage ,lack of motivation fear of punishment unsuitable school timing irrelevant course content, communication gap between teacher and student as the major factor Srivastav(1991) notes that the retention of tribal girls in higher classes is very low ,Ghosh-Maulik(1992) speaks about big difference between the enrolment and real dropouts among the tribal girls . A status paper by tribal welfare department GoO(1994) on tribal Education for all by 2000 A.D shows a number of educational problems i.e. inadequate educational institution. Infrastructure, separate hostel for girls and boys, administrative problems are the causes of low enrolment and dropout . Rout and Mohanty (1994) worked on educational development of kutia kandha tribes gives importance of school building , staff position ,furniture, games and sports materials science apparatus, textbooks drinking water facilities and stress on the cluster approach for spreading education among these tribes Panda (1998) under took a vast study in odisha and finds that language and inadequate availability of education facilities, lack of motivation factor are the major impediments against tribal education .Kundu(2003) emphasis on

training of teachers in tribal dialects .Behra and Mohanty (2005) conducted a study on status and empowerment of the girl child have shown a comparative picture on the factors responsible for literacy and dropout Mohanty and Biswal (2007) concerned with the gender discrimination in caste Hindu and Tribal context, The literacy level of women is much less than their male counter parts. Mohaptra (2007) conducted a study on primitive tribes namely bonda .Juang and Dongaria Kandha. He finds that in pen and paper school building are there in many villages but practically these do not exist. Teachers are not attend the school regularly Mishra (2008) has evaluated the NEPGEL programme of Odisha and finds that the enrolment of tribal girls are increased in some tribal belts in some areas the result is so and so. In phulbani district the enrolment is decreased Mohanty and Biswal (2009) focused on the schools performance of two government schools. Their observation is the performance of school running under ST and SC department is better than others. They show indifferent attitude of parents towards education, poor economic condition of parent's engagement of children in agricultural activities, disinterest of children in study, lack of sufficient in teachers, lack of play ground are the pivotal causes of drop out among the tribal children .In another study(2009)which makes a comparison of the performance of the schools running under the school and mass education department and private bodies ,they have also found more or less similar reasons that are responsible for the low enrolment, irregular attendance and dropout among the ST children of the said two neighbouring states

Raibol is small village located in Kamakshyanagar Block of Dhenkanal district, Orissa with total 237 families residing. The Raibol village has population of 976 of which 497 are males while 479 are females as per Population Census 2011. In Raibol village population of children with age 0-6 is 117 which make up 11.99 % of total population of village. Child Sex Ratio for the Raibol as per census is 950, higher than Orissa average of 941. Raibol village has higher literacy rate compared to Orissa. In 2011, literacy rate of Raibol village was 81.14 % compared to 72.87 % of Orissa. In Raibol Male literacy stands at 90.39 % while female literacy rate was 71.56 %. As per district profile and Panchyati Raj department of odisha , Raibol village is covered with maximum no juang tribes with hamlet namely, Bhalumunda, jharan sahi Koriapal Hardgari administrated by Sarpanch who is elected representative of village.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the enrolment status of tribal girls in Raibol high school
2. To find out the causes of low enrolment and drop out of tribal girls in Raibol high school
3. To suggest measure for high enrolment and reduce drop out among tribal girls of Raibol Highschool

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the percentage of enrolment of tribal girls in Raiblo highschool of Dhenkanal district
2. What are the causes of low enrolment of tribal girls of Raibol high school
3. What are the causes of drop out of tribal girls in Raibol high school
4. What will be the measures for high enrolment and reducing drop out among tribal girls of raibol high school

METHODOLOGY

The researcher follows the case study method for conducting the study. The Raibol High school was taken as a case. All the ST girls enrolled in the Raibol High school were taken as sample of the study. Further the Head master of the concerned school, 7 teachers of that school and parents of the ST girls were taken for the study. A simple semi structured interview schedule were developed and administered to collect the data from parent's teachers and ST girls. A focus group discussion was also held for different groups separately in the high school campus.

Findings

DEMEOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF THE SAMPLE HIGH SCHOOL

Raibol high school is situated in the village raibol head quarter of raibol panchayat belongs to Dhenkanal District of odisha . The school has three class room one office room one teacher's common room and one headmaster room with RCC building .The school has no toilet facilities for boys and girls .the school has no science laboratory, computer lab and no library. The researcher found there is no games and sports instrument for both boys and girls. so far as teacher is concerned two arts TGT , one Sanskrit one Hindi teacher and one physical education teachers are working in the school . no science teachers(both PCM and CBZ) are found in that school . Hostel facilities are not available for boys and girls. Teachers quarter are also not available in the school so the teachers from outside the village return their home after taking lunch. The researcher observes in his one month staying at the school campus that the teachers are not coming to the school regularly. Though it is a block grant school and teachers are not getting full salary from the government they are engaged with their other work they treat teaching is there subsidiary work

STUDENT STRENGTH IN SAMPLE SCHOOL

Enrolment is a most vital component of the whole educational system in secondary level. more particularly it act in a major way on regulating the overall attendance and retention level or in other words the liking of girls on remaining out of school or in the school during the school days

Table-6

Year	VIII							
	SC		ST		OBC		Total	
	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls
2011-12	1	1	19	20	9	9	29	30
2012-13	1	1	8	15	9	6	18	22
2013-14	2	1		7	4	11	15	2
2014-15	1		17	11	6	5	24	16

From the above table it is found that in the year 2011-12 the enrolment of girls in class VIII is high i.e 20 in number where as the enrolment of ST girls in 2013-14 academic year is very low .

in the present academic year 11 ST girl students are admitted in the class VIII .Similarly in class IX the no of ST girls in the academic year 2011-12 were 10 which is given in the table no and in the academic year 2014-15 the enrolment of ST girls was 08 which is very low in comparisons to other category

Table-7

YEAR	IX									
	SC		ST		OBC		General		Total	
	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls
2011-12	1	1	17	10	6	11	0	1	25	22
2012-13	1	1	19	19	9	9			29	29
2013-14	2	1	9	20	8	6	0	2	19	29
2014-15	3	1	16	8	7	15			26	24

The table given below is clearly indicates about the enrolment status of Rabiol high school in class X with different category. The no of ST girls is 11 in the academic year 2011-12 where as the no in the academic year 2014-15 is 17 out of total 29 girls

Table-8

YEAR	X							
	SC		ST		OBC		Total	
	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls
2011-12	0	1	13	11	11	4	24	16
2012-13	1	1	17	9	6	11	24	21
2013-14	1	1	17	15	8	9	26	25
2014-15	2	1	1	17	7	6	19	29

The above table speak that for the current academic year i.e 2014-15 the proportion of ST girls student is more than their boys counterparts in class X

EDUCATIONAL AND OCCUPATIONAL STANDARDS OF PARENTS

It is found that 45 % parents were below high school qualification, 48% are not going to school or not any type of formal qualification and 7% parents are above matriculate. So far as occupation is concerned 42% of the parents were agricultural labourer, 48% are collecting forest product and selling it to the nearby market .10% are engaged with making leaf cups and plates

Causes of Low Enrolments of Tribal Girls

The causes of non enrolment were taken by the parents. 65% parents opined that they have disinterest in studies ,14% parents says girls are required for household works, 7% respondents also opined that education is not considered necessary for girls where as 9% parents gives their opinion that girls are required for the care of siblings and 5% parents said that the cost is too much . While the researcher taken the opinion of teachers the same causes are found for the non enrolment of girls in high school however one more cause for non enrolment of tribal girls is found in the focus group discussion of teachers that societal and parental consideration of ‘no necessity of education for girls’ similarly on FGD of parents the core one is the permanent changing of home on the part of a girl, often develop a idea that spending the hard earned resource on the education of girls would be nothing but an unwise act of sending girls to school some oriya saying that (I) jhia janam paragharku (ii) jhia janam Handishalaku the 1 st one is saying about the daughters are born to leave their parental home after their marriage , the second one specifies confinement of duties of the girls only to cook food for the family members.

So far as absenteeism is concerned, a girl child may absent in school in various reasons and she intends to take leave from the schools she has to officially place reason for the same. But practically the official procedure is not followed by the class teacher or by the head master of the school. therefore the natural reasons of absenteeism was collected by the focus group discussion among the students ,Though it is hard for a child to rember the reasons for all her absence , here it is tried out to find out the reasons of last there absence .in total there 11 reasons have come out in the focus group discussion these are Agricultural necessities, call to sit with younger babies, observance of rituals or fairs or festivals either at household or nearby village , call to company her mother for collection of forest product i.e. collection of “tola and Mahula” call for making leaf cups and plates, call for going to nearby market for selling of forest products and purchasing weekly grocery ,dress and other requirements ,call to remain at home because of illness of family members , failure to do home work . washing of school dress and conflict with peers

Causes Of Dropout of tribal girls

In order to find out the dropout rate of tribal girls researcher consulted with the concerned class teacher and the head master of raibol high school In class x only 03 ST girls were dropout while in class ix 07 girls are dropout in the academic year 2014-15 . the concerned head master opined that though the dropout is low in class x but the ST girls were regularly irregular in class. After verification of records of previous three years it is found that most of the tribal girls are not appearing the annual HSC examination .As per the teachers of the high school though they are poor and not able to pay the exam fees they are debar from the annual HSC exam . Drop out among tribal girls of curse takes a number of causes. while discussing with parents , students and teachers in a focus group discussion it is found that , they are not interested in studies , getting married , requirement for seasonal work, requirement for the care of siblings , financial weakness working as earners of families, difficulties of learning and engaged in household work are the common causes of dropout of tribal girls in raibol high school .in one case one girl is point out that her father forced to help mother in house hold work and ultimately she is drop out in class x . while another case one girl said that her family is very poor and daily she and her mother goes to forest and collect the leaf and dry wood and in the second half they sale it in “Mathakarogla “ the nearby market so it is impossible to attain the class regularly on her part. one parent of the concerned school opined that his daughter has attained adulthood and he is searching a groom for his daughter so he is disinterest to send his daughter regularly to the class. Similarly another parent i.e one mother said my daughter has no friends to accompany for attending the school

though the school is 1.5 km from the house and the approach road is surrounded with dense jungle it is not possible to send her daughter to the school .

Conclusion and Recommendations

From the above discussion made in the present piece of study it comes to know that government of odisha has taken a number of steps to bring the schedule tribe educationally forward moreover various gender specific schemes and programmes has been implemented in secondary schools for encouraging girls enrolment and reducing dropout rates. However illiteracy and poor economic condition of parents who don't have right perception of modern education and lack of sufficient awareness on the government provisions and other such benefits on the employment opportunities for the educated ST girls is a cause of not successful for bringing ST girls educationally at par with others .The ST girls children drop themselves out from schools for various factors in the concerned school so these need to be set right scientifically with locally On the basis of the findings of the study the researcher recommend some suggestions

The Self Help Group of the juang community should be involved for orienting parents to send their children to the school. For the financial point of view school should provide the scholarship timely and particularly the headmaster should help financially to the needy poor girls who's academic achievement is above average by diverting some money from other fund .The school conduct health check-up camp at least twice in a year by coordinating with local doctors ANMS The headmaster must arrange extra classes for them who have some learning difficulties .The school should arrange regular parents meeting at least once in a month so that the community will be mobilised .Though most of the students are from tribal community the holidays should be fixed by the school keeping in view of the festivals of tribal's not the state government rules. The school timing should be reduced and the closing time of school should be 3 PM instead of 4 PM because the girls are coming from jungles will reach the home in time the teacher should teach the lesson with sufficient TLM based on tribal arts and cultures

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